

Garvan Institute
of Medical Research

Costs of Running Production Genomics Workflows On-Premise as well as on Commercial Clouds

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Project Goal

While the field of genome analysis is rapidly evolving, a number of tools have matured to become the *de facto* standard. The Garvan Institute has rapidly grown to become Australia's leading genome-powered medical research institute, and this has meant that we have moved production genome analysis workflows out of the hands of individual researchers. Instead, these workflows are built by engineers to be run at scale on-premise, on commercial clouds (Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure) and at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI).

Here we pose the following questions:

- Since we built our 5000 core on-premise computational infrastructure using grants - what does it cost us to run these workflows at Garvan, and how do these costs compare when running the identical workflows on AWS, Azure and the NCI.
- What are the underlying costs of running these analyses that include, power, maintenance, staffing etc?

Approach

Garvan's Data Sciences Platform works in the areas of production workflows, user-interfaces, foundational computing resources and data sharing. The Data Intensive Computer Engineering (DICE) team within the DSP designed and built our on-premise, grant-funded, 5000 core computing infrastructure and support our parallel file storage system. The team also builds and runs production workflows as a service and continues to do so at scale. This includes the 4000 whole human genomes of the [Medical Genome Reference Bank](#) cohort on Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure, as well as thousands more genomes on-premises as well as the NCI in Canberra.

We looked to use a single source code to deploy our analysis on AWS, Azure and the NCI. The specific analysis that we used is our best-practice whole genome and exome workflows that essentially comprise the running of the tools BWA-MEM together with the Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK). As we looked to understand the underlying costs of running these analyses we came up with a number of key questions:

- Capital versus Operational expenditure
 - At Garvan HPC (and IT more generally) is purchased on a capital basis, but cloud is purchased on an operational expenditure basis.
- Data egress
 - All cloud vendors charge a “tax” for downloading data from their infrastructure.
- Central grant/funding agencies
 - Grants (for compute) are traditionally on the basis of capital (rather than operational expenditure).
 - Grants are used to buy physical things whose lifetime extends beyond the lifetime of the grant. This leads to a mindset about ‘ownership’ of assets and the fact that these are ‘free’ to use. Grants are used to buy storage that researchers use to secure their long-term data. In a pay-as-you-go model, when a grant runs out the data could go away. What offerings could the ARDC make to get around this issue?
- Budgeting - At Garvan budgets are allocated on an annual basis. If research computing costs (HPC and others) is to move into Opex, how do Garvan researchers secure long-term funding commitments to insulate themselves from the vagaries of the annual budgeting cycle? In the on-premise model this is not so much of a problem. Once the hardware is paid for, the cost savings associated with switching it off are generally small, compared to the loss in output.
- Cost management
 - If research computing is delivered via pay-as-you go, then researchers need to be more actively concerned with managing their budget. In contrast, in an on-premise world, all a Principal Investigator has to worry about is the cost of the original capital investment and then not worry any more. This is not the case with cloud.
 - How can researchers more accurately predict their cost exposure?
- Cloud is a new provisioning and usage model for the researchers. There is now an increased (overwhelming) level of choice. What tools should be developed to help users decide on what services to use?

Garvan also had conversations with [Red Oak Consulting](#), experts in HPC procurement in the UK in order to refine it’s thinking in this area.

Findings

From a single source code repository we dockerised the code and deployed the identical code base on AWS and Azure. The process was mostly straightforward with both cloud providers offering excellent support. We also used the same code base to port the code to run using [Singularity](#) on Garvan’s on-premise HPC cluster. The NCI does not currently support the running of Docker or Singularity on its infrastructure. We were fortunate to work closely with the

NCI team in order to develop our solution. Optimisation of this work is still on-going but performance at the NCI and initial costs are very encouraging (Table 1).

We found that it was substantially cheaper to run whole genome workflows on Garvan’s on-premise infrastructure at this time than anywhere else. However, it also became clear to us that the discrepancies in cost of running Garvan’s research computing infrastructure (Figure 1 B) and those across the industry (Figure 1 A) are due to a number of key structural aspects of the Garvan team: they have zero redundancy of tasks, and rely on zero commercial support for running its services other than hardware support.

Figure 1. Typical on-premise data centre costs. Costs identified by Red Oak Consulting (A) are contrasted with the Garvan Institute’s on-premise solution (B).

Whole Genome Workflow	AWS Cost	Azure	NCI	Garvan
Wall time (hours)	21	22	12	11
CPU cost (\$AUD)	\$10	\$14	\$17	\$3 (estimated)
Egress	\$30	\$28	zero	zero
Total	\$40-\$45	\$43-\$46	\$17	\$3 (estimated)

Table 1. Cost of computing whole genomes on different infrastructures. While Garvan comes out the cheapest, and while it boasts of having zero egress costs it pays for a dedicated (10 Gigabit) link to the NCI which has not been factored into the costs.

Garvan entire research computing infrastructure was funded by research and infrastructure grants.

- The research infrastructure (used for running production workflows) comprises approximately 80 computer servers all connected via 25 Gigabit Ethernet to the node. The network comprises 5 (25 GigE) leaf switches and 2 x 100 GigE spine switches. Three generations of computer nodes exist:
 - 2012 Dell C6145 servers comprising 64 cores of AMD Interlagos and 512 GB RAM, and 5 TB disk
 - 2015 Xenon (Supermicro) servers each with dual socket 2x 14 cores (56 hyperthreaded), 512 GB RAM and 20 TB NVMe storage.
 - 2018 Dell servers each with 2x20 cores (80 hyperthreads), 768 GB RAM, and 24 TB of local NVMe storage.
 - We also operate a 1 Petabyte Panasas (panfs) parallel file system.

Analysis and/or Emerging Themes

As we explored this space deeper we realised the complexity of challenges we face in achieving a clear decision regarding the usage of cloud in favour of our own on-premise research computing infrastructure. We also found discussions with Red Oak Consulting quite confronting in terms of highlighting that:

- Our HPC is always the “wrong” size:
 - When our queues are always full we lose value to our scientific enterprise.
 - When our queues are empty - multiplier effect impact on the costs per cycle. Something we haven’t factored into our analysis.

Superficially, Garvan’s low costs of computing genomes on premise sounds very encouraging. However when we contrasted our team’s make-up (two talented engineers) with mostly non-redundant tasks it became increasingly clear to us that our services are particularly vulnerable. We also have become increasingly mindful that while Garvan is competitive in attracting scientific talent, in the recruitment of engineers it is up against the cloud providers,

and other tech giants and financial services. In terms of remuneration, Garvan also cannot compete with these companies, and this fact alone may result in us (like colleagues around the world) not being able to support our own infrastructure. This will drive us towards running increasing numbers of workloads on the cloud.

Opportunities for the ARDC

We see an idealised ecosystem evolving where a hybrid computing model exists that comprises small domain expertise like ours at Garvan that work closely with Tier 1 supercomputing facilities (the NCI in our case) and commercial clouds. From our perspective cloud provides the best opportunities where large egress costs are avoided by deleting input and intermediate files and only downloading results. An example of this ecosystem is shown in Figure 2. The opportunity for the ARDC is the growth of a Data Commons Economy. In this model “if the data can pay - the data can stay”. Computation is only there to extract value out of the data. In the case of genome workflows this means the identification of genetic variants in a genome. It is through the growth of cloud expertise and the nurturing of expert groups (like Garvan and others) as well as supporting data sets at the NCI that the extraordinary potential of the ARDC may be realised.

Figure 2. An ARDC interconnected ecosystem. The ARDC could support the creation or storage of datasets of tangible value at eg. the NCI. Expert groups such as Garvan’s Data Sciences Platform would drive value from these data using diverse computing approaches with both Garvan and the NCI have fast connections (direct connects) to commercial clouds. Cloud usage would be primarily to support the bursting of increased data processing needs. To eliminate egress costs all input and intermediate files deleted on the cloud and only results returned.

Issues and Barriers to Goals

Our containerised workflows ran from end-to-end on standalone virtual machines (VMs) in the cloud, and using Singularity on our on premise cluster. The efficiencies of the code is of very little interest to the cloud providers. In contrast, the NCI is obsessed about efficient codes running on their infrastructure, and since the NCI does not support the running of containerised code on their infrastructure - it became increasingly clear that engineering a solution on the NCI was a specialised task. Something that could only be justified for well established workflows that need to run at scale, and in contrast to one-off analyses.